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Assessing The Quality Of Electrical Wiring Materials Used In Residential Buildings In Benue State, Nigeria: Addressing The Issue Of Counterfeit Electrical Supplies

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ABSTRACT

Utilization of substandard electrical materials in electrical wiring had become a major engineering issue, primarily due materials and public health hazards it poses. This study investigated the electrical wires standards, utilized for wiring operation in Benue State, Central Nigeria. Four frequently utilized electrical wires for electrical wiring (1.5mm², 2.5mm², 4mm², and 6 mm²) were sampled across the studied region (Benue State), and their size and electrical resistivity were measured in agreement with standard procedures. The experimental findings revealed that the mean electrical resistivity results of the 1.5, 2.5, 4 and 6 mm² wires 2.04 x10⁻⁷, 1.92 x10⁻⁷, 1.75 x10⁻⁷ and 1.72 x10⁻⁷ Ωmm, respectively. Findings obtained from the scientific investigation indicated that, most of the electrical wire's size and electrical resistivity were unable to meet the NIS approved recommendations. With respect to the conclusions of this study, it is recommended that electrical products monitoring agencies should intensify the fight against inferior electrical materials, to avoid consistent power outage and looming dangers in Nigeria.

Keywords: Counterfeiting, electrical materials, electrical resistivity, power failure, public menace

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is currently facing substantial challenges, posed by the rapid proliferation of substandard and counterfeit electrical materials, partially blamed on quackery, corruption, ignorance and poor economic situation (Obukoeroro and Uguru, 2021; Ezeanochie and Onu,2024). According to the Standard organization of Nigeria (SON), majority of the inferior electrical materials and accessories utilized in Nigeria, are smuggled from Asia continent due to the Nigeria's porous borders (Schneider Electric, 2015; Odoh *et al.*, 2022). Utilization of fake electrical materials has led to loss of human lives, and also resulted

in the devastation of assets, amounting to billions of naira, primarily through power outage, electrocution, and electric fires. These poor quality materials are often masked as truly certified materials, with forged manufacturer's address, logos and quality seals; but they are prone to short-circuiting, microstructural failure, macro-structural rupture, arcing and overheating (Adekunle et al., 2016; Uguru and Obukoeroro, 2020)

Substandard material is a principal cause of electrical/mechanical systems failures, leading to disruption of electrical power distribution, materials loss and electrical fires. According to Odoh et al. (2022), conductor and insulating materials used for electrical applications in southern Nigeria, fell below the approved NIS: 172 standard recommendations; hence, they are susceptible to malfunctioning and system failures. Nigeria is flooded with counterfeited copper (Cu) and aluminum (Al) electrical materials - wires and cables. This and coupled with illegal installations are partially attributed to the incidences of electrical fires and frequent outages. Quack manufacturers use copper/aluminum dressed iron as pure Al or Cu during the production of electrical materials. Therefore, these material conspicuously failed to meet the quality certification, approved by Nigerian Industrial Standards (NIS), Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and other international regulatory agencies (Obukoeroro and Uguru, 2021; Viktorovych, 2022; Anyigor et al., 2024).

Recently (within the last two decades), there are numerous researches on the integrity of electrical wires and cables, employed for electrical installation operations across different regions of Nigeria (Obukoeroro and Uguru, 2021; Odoh et al., 2022; Ezeanochie and Onu, 2024). However, related literature search reveals a conspicuous information dearth about Benue State of Nigeria, despite its rapid industrialization and growing trend of residential buildings. Therefore, the main goal of this research is to access the standard of electrical wires/cables, used for electrical installations across Benue State, Central Nigeria. Additionally, the study will focus on identifying the pervasiveness of counterfeited electrical supplies in the region.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area

This research was done within Benue State of Nigeria, which is located in north-central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The state has total landmass of approximately 34,000 km², human population of approximately 5.9 million, predominantly known for food production, and several universities, polytechnics and other higher institutions (Uguru et al., 2024). These had contributed immensely, to the rapid increment in residential and industrial buildings construction. This is the primary reason why Benue State was chosen as the study area, based on the urban expansion and surge in substandard construction materials.

Materials sampling

Four commonly utilized electrical wires (1.5mm, 2.5mm², 4mm² and 6 mm²) were selected from ten (10) major electrical markets/stores across the state. During the sampling operation, these specimens were randomly sampled from the electrical stops, at the rate of three samples per each wire size.

Laboratory tests

The laboratory tests were conducted in harmony with the NIS approved procedures. Each wire strand size was measured with a digital caliper, and the area was computed through Equation 1 (Odoh et al., 2022).

$$Area = \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$$

Where: d ~ diameter

Electrical resistance and resistivity

The wire’s electrical resistance and electrical resistivity (ρ) was determined in accordance with IEEE 400 approved guidelines, through the formula shown in Equation 2 (Obukoeroro and Uguru, 2021).

$$\text{Resistivity } (\rho) = \frac{RA}{l}$$

2.

Where: R ~ resistance, d ~ strand diameter, l ~ length

Data analysis

The one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to statistically analyze the laboratory results, to determine the impact of the sampling locations on the electrical properties of the electrical wires.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wire sizes

The one-way ANOVA result of the influence of the sampling location on the wire size is presented in Table 1. It was noted that sampling location has significant influence on the wire size ($p \leq 0.05$). Moreover, the descriptive statistics presented in Table 2, revealed that the sizes of the 1.5, 2.5, 4 and 6 mm² wires sampled ranged from 1.15 to 1.61 mm², 1.79 to 2.63 mm², 3.21 to 4.23 mm² and 4.95 to 6.11 mm², respectively. This depicted that most of the wire sampled failed to attained NIS:172 recommendation for electrical wires, suitable for electrical installation operation. This research outcome aligned with earlier findings of Onyekachi and Nduka (2019) and Odoh *et al.* (2022), when bulk of the electrical wires/cables sold and utilized in southern Nigeria, were unable to meet international approved wire sizes for electrical wiring.

Table 1: ANOVA outcome of impact of the sampling point on the wire size

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p value
Between Groups	322.28	3	107.43	1944.54	9.32E-97*
Within Groups	7.01	116	0.060		
Total	329.29	119			

* = significant at $p \leq 0.05$ according to DMRT

Table 2: Descriptive summary of the wire sizes (n = 30)

Size	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min.	Max.
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1.5 mm ²	1.43	0.11037	1.39	1.47	1.15	1.61
2.5 mm ²	2.28	0.21889	2.22	2.37	1.79	2.63
4 mm ²	3.86	0.22502	3.78	3.94	3.21	4.23
6 mm ²	5.73	0.36200	5.60	5.87	4.95	6.11

Electrical resistivity

Table 3 shows the results of the impact of the sampling location on the wire’s electrical resistivity. It was observed that sampling location significantly influenced the wire resistivity ($p \leq 0.05$). Additionally, Table 4 displays the descriptive statistics summary of the wire resistivity values, and the outcomes revealed that the mean ρ values for the 1.5, 2.5, 4 and 6 mm² wire samples were 2.04×10^{-7} , 1.92×10^{-7} , 1.75×10^{-7} and 1.72×10^{-7} Ω mm, respectively. The range of the ρ results obtained in this study (Table 4) revealed that most of the wires samples were substandard, and failed to meet NIS approved standards set for wiring operations. Specifically, the NIS recorded that the electrical resistivity values of 1.5, 2.5, 4 and 6 mm² wires, should not exceed 2.0×10^{-7} Ω mm, 1.85×10^{-7} Ω mm and 1.70×10^{-7} Ω mm, respectively (Odoh *et al.*, 2022). Despite their tiny size and the typical ambient temperature ($32 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$) at which the resistance of the wires was measured, the wire's high resistance can be linked to its general high

resistivity. Electrical fires can occur when high electrical resistivity wires are subjected to electrical loads because of their small surface areas and high resistance, which allow them to heat up quickly. Electrical Engineering (2020) stated that high ρ values creates significant voltage drops across electrical installations; thereby, resulting in malfunctioning of the electrical system.

Remarkably, Obukoeroro and Uguru (2021) in their investigation into electrical accessories reported similar results, for electrical wires utilized for electrical installations in southern Nigeria. The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) stated that all electrical conductors must have electrical properties, which are in conformity with internationally regulatory bodies (NERC, 2014). Furthermore, the results depicted that the smaller sizes wire tend to have higher electrical resistivity, when compared to the larger sizes wire. Likewise, the higher ρ recorded in this investigation is an indication the wires were not manufactured from pure Cu metal (Adekoya, 2019). Although, the Nigeria standard regulatory agencies are sanitizing the country of faked electrical products, more efforts are required to get rid of the country of substandard electrical materials.

Table 3: The ANOVA of the sampled electrical wires

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	2.08E-14	3	6.94E-15	75.82	3.21E-27*
Within Groups	1.06E-14	116	9.16E-17		
Total	3.15E-14	119			

* = significant at $p \leq 0.05$ according to DMRT

Table 4: The sampled electrical wires electrical resistivity ($\times 10^{-7} \Omega \text{mm}$)

Size (mm ²)	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min.	Max.
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1.5	2.04 ^c	0.90	2.01	2.07	1.87	2.22
2.5	1.92 ^b	0.59	1.90	1.95	1.79	2.03
4	1.75 ^a	0.90	1.72	1.79	1.56	1.92
6	1.72 ^a	0.13	1.67	1.76	1.41	1.94

n = 30, columns having similar letter signifies that the values are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$)

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted out to evaluate the standard of metallic conductors widely utilized for electrical wiring in Nigeria. Four electrical wires (1.5 mm², 2.5 mm², 4 mm² and 6 mm²) were sampled from Benue State, and their strand diameter and electrical resistivity, determined in accordance with NIS and ASTM approved procedures. Outcomes of the laboratory evaluations depicted that most of the wires were substandard, since their sizes and electrical resistivity failed to meet NIS standards. Furthermore, the results highlighted that the smaller wire sizes (1.5 mm² and 2.5 mm²) had higher resistivity, which is hazardous to electrical installations Electrical fire and other failures tend to break out easily in smaller diameter wires with higher electrical resistivity, primarily due to the occurrence of circuit overheating resulting from higher electrical resistance. Interestingly, the results of this study have revealed the necessity of intensifying efforts to weed the region of substandard electrical materials, as this will safeguard electrical facilities and public health.

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